
Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some number lower than 10. For example; six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India. 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Gibberellin response of japonica-indica hybrids in Korean rice cultivars

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The recent rapid increase in rice yields in Korea is based mainly on the successful release of new japonica-indica hybrid cultivars. These cultivars were bred using IRRI semidwarf lines, whose semidwarf gene comes from Dee-geo-woo-gen and is believed to limit gibberellin (GA) biosynthesis. Hence, these new hybrid cultivars should respond more to applied GA.

To check this effect, we compared the response to GA of the second leaf sheaths of japonica-indica hybrid cultivars with that of some japonicas and indicas. The cultivars used were japonicas: 1) Milseong, 2) Milyang 15, 3) Mankyeong, 4) Koshiji-wase, 5) Nipponbare, 6) Eiko; indicas: 7) Early Tall Peta, 8) Dee-geo-woo-gen, 9) Mao-tsu-tao, 10) Kaladumai, 11) Century Patna 231, 12) Dular, 13) CO 13, 14) Hawaragepoek; and hybrids: 15) Tongil, 16) Yushin, 17) Milyang 21, 18) Milyang 23, 19) Milyang 30, 20) Milyang 42, 21) Suweon 258, 22) Suweon 264, 23) Nopung.

The results (see figure) indicated a negative correlation between the length of the second leaf sheaths and the

Relationship between length of second leaf sheath (LSLS) and response to gibberellin (1 ppm) of japonica, indica, and japonica-indica hybrid rice cultivars. ○ = japonica, ▼ = indica, ● = japonica-indica hybrid. For numbering of cultivars, see text.

response to GA. Most japonicas had short leaf sheaths and high GA response, whereas indicas, except Dee-geo-woo-gen which possesses a semidwarf gene, had long leaf sheaths and low GA response. The hybrid cultivars had short leaf sheaths but showed different reactions — one gave a very high GA response and the other the lowest response. The first group probably possesses a semidwarf gene of Dee-geo-woo-gen which limits GA biosynthesis; the latter probably possesses some genes that lack the site of action of GA.

Japonica-indica hybrids belonging to the latter group are important as new dwarf gene sources for rice breeding, although the genetic basis for such is unknown. ■

PY1 or Pudukai Ponni — a new rice for late samba

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The northeast monsoon period (Sep-Oct to Dec-Jan) in the Coromandal coastal belt of Pondicherry is characterized by low temperatures (25-30°C), reduced

sunlight duration (5.5-8.3 h/day), monsoon cloudiness, and high rainfall (927-1,144 mm in 50-53 rainy days). Pest incidence is heavy during the period. Despite such unfavorable conditions, almost 70% of the cultivable area in the Union Territory of Pondicherry is under monsoon rice because of heavy monsoon showers and excessive moisture.

Among the medium-duration rice var-